

ARCHITECTURE FOR THE UN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

- A MAP OF GLOBAL EFFORTS

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Royal Danish Academy of Fine Arts
Schools of Architecture, Design and Conservation*

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INTRODUCTION

The UIA2023 world congress 'SUSTAINABLE FUTURES - LEAVE NO ONE BEHIND' promotes, discusses, develops and showcases architecture as a crucial tool to achieving the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals by 2030.

Society finds itself in a situation of crisis. The real challenges we stand before as we enter an era of climate breakdown and biodiversity loss, coupled with exponential population growth, accelerated urbanisation, escalated social division and inequality are putting unprecedented pressures on the way we live and how we see our future. Around the world campaigners, cities, institutions and governments are declaring a state of emergency. In this unprecedented moment, the defining question for architects, urban designers and landscape architects is: what are the radical measures by which we affect a step change in the way we think, design and build our societies.

The overarching goal of the UIA2023 Congress - Science Track is to foster the knowledge needed for architecture and the built environment to understand, build and fulfill its active role in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals. The congress articulates the special agency architecture and the built environment have in shaping our societies; the way we live, the way we interact and the way we build and how changing our practices can lead to a sustainable, equitable and inclusive future for all.

CONTENTS

UIA 2023 INTERNATIONAL MAPPING	7
DEFINING SIX PANELS FOR UIA2023 SCIENCE TRACK	9
DESCRIPTIONS OF THE SIX PANELS	11
MAP OF INTERNATIONAL ACTORS	19
ACTOR STATISTICS	20
PANEL 1: DESIGN FOR CLIMATE ADAPTATION	23
PANEL 2: DESIGN FOR RETHINKING RESOURCES	41
PANEL 3: DESIGN FOR RESILIENT COMMUNITIES	61
PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH	81
PANEL 5: DESIGN FOR INCLUSIVITY	95
PANEL 6: DESIGN FOR PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE	119

UIA 2023 INTERNATIONAL MAPPING

In order to build a strong understanding of the current state of the art in architectural research and industry efforts we have created an international mapping of over 100 researchers and practitioners currently working to achieve the sustainable development goals. The mapping shows the diversity of knowledge that the field of architecture embodies as well as the breadth of contributions we can achieve. From formulating overarching strategies for city planning, environmental design or systems design to the specific design of the single community, building or home, architecture from all regions is present across all 17 Sustainable Development Goals.

The international mapping presents an image of the nature of existing efforts, the problem space addressed, the discourse and the methods by which this research is undertaken.

The mapping is created so as to ensure that the UIA2023 panels are well grounded in existing architectural research communities and to understand their global distribution. We have made an effort to find representation for all panel across the five UIA regions.

The mapping allows us to:

- Ground the panel descriptions in existing research trajectories and efforts
- Understand the scientific output of the UIA 2023 Science Track
- Understand participation in 2023
- Identify keynote speakers and invited presenters

ENVIRONMENT

Technology

Ecology

RESOURCES

Governmental

The Social

HUMANS

DEFINING SIX PANELS FOR UIA 2023 SCIENCE TRACK

Architecture affects our actions across environment, resource and society.

The Science Track is divided into six panels that together frame the 17 UN Sustainable Development Goals. The panels are developed using Professor Katherine Richardson's model for understanding the overarching strategising of the goals as an interfacing between the needs of the planet and the needs of humanity. By moving from concerns of the environment, through resource to the needs of humanity, the goal are grouped into topics that engage existing research communities in academia and industry.

Our aim is to articulate the panels to frame the special agency architecture and the built environment have across the Goals - shaping our society; the way we live, the way we interact and the way we build - and how the effort to change our practices can lead to a sustainable, equitable and inclusive future for all.

THE SIX PANELS

1 Design For Climate Adaptation

2 Design For Rethinking Resources

3 Design For Resilient Communities

4 Design For Health

5 Design For Inclusivity

6 Design For Partnerships Of Change

PANEL 1 DESIGN FOR CLIMATE ADAPTATION

The built environment exists within a larger, more powerful natural ecosystem. As climate patterns change, so must the role of buildings and how they interface with their environment. 'Design for Climate Adaptation' includes both high and low-tech solutions to environmental design which work to make buildings smarter and more self-sufficient. New adaptive methods for rainwater harvesting, heating and cooling, living roofs and new renewable energy technologies allow us to rethink how a building is operated and how it can contribute to its environment. Outside of the building, climate change is addressed by resilient landscaping; design for rising sea levels, flooding and stormwater protection as well as desertification, drought and wildfire. 'Design for Climate Adaptation' allows us to mitigate against changing environments and encourage a symbiotic ecology that allows for peaceful and cooperative adaptation of the built environment.

PANEL 2 DESIGN FOR RETHINKING RESOURCES

Design shapes our world, from the places we live in to objects we use every day. As we grow more aware of the limits of our planet's resources, shifting from an exploitative to a restorative, regenerative and circular design ideology becomes necessary. 'Design for Rethinking Resources' examines approaches to resourcefulness in our practice. It includes the materials we use: the engineering of new materials, recycling of waste and use of bio-based materials lends the possibility to start the cycle of production sustainably. The methods we apply: from computational design and digital technologies, to crafts revival and vernacular building techniques allow us to innovate localised design solutions while also supporting local economies. And finally, the life we expect of our building: from design for disassembly, programmed decay, life cycle analysis and rethinking the durability of our building - 'Design for Rethinking Resources' means re-assessing all aspects of the production and consumption cycles with sustainability in mind.

PANEL 3 DESIGN FOR RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Sustainable futures are dependent on the thoughtful planning of cities and communities. Rapid urbanisation and high-density cities are putting unprecedented pressures on the way we live. 'Design for Resilient Communities' investigates multiple perspectives defining the way we live. It includes: Economic perspectives: how self-sustaining communities, responsible land use and transformation of existing building stock rethink the economies of our communities and allows us to change the long term benefits of inhabitants. Social perspectives: how the design of the public realm, both physical and digital, affects the way we live in our communities and how augmenting our lives with smart technologies can provide insight into wide-scale patterns changing the way we occupy and interact within the built environment. And environmental perspectives: how the infrastructures of our communities can be shaped to reduce our carbon footprint and allow green living. 'Design for Resilient Communities' asks how these perspectives can be developed and contribute to a more sustainable development of communities and urban space.

PANEL 4 DESIGN FOR HEALTH

The built environment affects our physical and mental health as humans. With increases in population and unequal infrastructure, considerations of preventable premature mortality are of major concern for sustainable futures. 'Design for Health' problematises what design for healthy communities can be. From the direct design of hospitals and places for healing to the strategic design of healthcare facilities to reduce the transmission of communicable disease or focus on special user groups such as HIV vulnerable groups or pregnant women, architecture contributes to the reduction of mortality rates. Beyond direct healthcare, taking action to improve basic infrastructure such as developing sewage systems for informal settlements or better building practices for disease prevention, sharply increases public health and wellbeing. Finally, design can promote individual health by shaping mobility and accessibility, creating spaces for an active outdoor life and ensuring indoor climate health and comfort. 'Design for Health' engages the breadth of society moving from the public efforts of healthcare provision to the well-being of each individual person.

PANEL 5 DESIGN FOR INCLUSIVITY

Escalating social division and inequality are putting pressures on the way we live and how we see our future. The ideal for a sustainable future is that no one is left behind and to endeavour to reach the furthest behind first. 'Design for Inclusivity' considers how a more egalitarian and humanitarian design ethos can be promoted: how architecture and the built environment can encourage awareness of and dialogue about the socio-economic and political division between the Global South and the Global North. It addresses universal design and the shaping of gender equal environments and it discusses how vulnerable and marginalised groups can be included through the careful consideration of cultural differences and strategies for cultural preservation. How social housing strategies and design of inclusive community buildings can work to cement cohesiveness across communities, how responsible improvement of informal settlements can stimulate social equality and how innovation can offer new solutions to emergency shelters, refugee housing and post disaster-regeneration. 'Design for inclusivity' ensures no one is left behind by critically addressing our understanding of design agency and re-drawing a more inclusive practice.

PANEL 6 DESIGN FOR PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

'Design for Partnerships of Change' happens when we collaboratively work towards peace, social justice, and a sustainable future with strong coalitions. Implementing changes requires partnerships between governments, the private sector and civil society. 'Design for Partnership of Change' examines how architecture and the built environment can encourage such partnerships, the agency they embody and the results they can achieve. Architecture can be an important driver for change in its ability to be an instrument of governance from the forming of local policies, private-public partnerships to the creation of participatory design methods for democratic and collaborative community planning. It can be a critical geopolitical method for cultural discourse and human rights, creating awareness of territory and border issues. And it can be used as a voice to start interdisciplinary dialogues by critical curation and dissemination. 'Design for Partnerships of Change' challenges the boundaries of architectural design, its repercussions and our understanding of why, how and by whom architecture is produced.

UIA MEMBER REGIONS AND MAP OF INTERNATIONAL ACTORS

REGION 1 WESTERN EUROPE
REGION 2 EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
REGION 3 THE AMERICAS
REGION 4 ASIA/OCEANIA
REGION 5 AFRICA

STATISTICS

BY REGION

REGION 1

Total Actors: 23
Male: 9
Female: 14

REGION 2

Total Actors: 20
Male: 5
Female: 15

REGION 3

Total Actors: 20
Male: 10
Female: 10

REGION 4

Total Actors: 21
Male: 13
Female: 8

REGION 5

Total Actors: 20
Male: 10
Female: 10

Total: 104
Male: 47
Female: 57

BY PANEL

Panel 1: Climate Adaptation

Total Actors: 16
Male: 9
Female: 7
Academic: 7
Industry-based: 9

Panel 2: Rethinking Resources

Total Actors: 18
Male: 12
Female: 6
Academic: 9
Industry-based: 9

Panel 3: Resilient Communities

Total Actors: 18
Male: 10
Female: 8
Academic: 8
Industry-based: 10

Panel 4: Design for Health

Total Actors: 12
Male: 6
Female: 6
Academic: 6
Industry-based: 6

Panel 5: Inclusivity

Total Actors: 22
Male: 5
Female: 17
Academic: 11
Industry-based: 11

Panel 6: Partnerships of Change

Total Actors: 18
Male: 5
Female: 13
Academic: 11
Industry-based: 7

**PANEL 1
DESIGN FOR
CLIMATE ADAPTATION**

KATHERINE RICHARDSON

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
COPENHAGEN, DENMARK

Biological Oceanographer and Expert on Sustainability

Professor in Biological Oceanography at the University of Copenhagen

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 13 - CLIMATE ACTION

Affiliations

- Former Chair of the Danish Commission on Climate Change Policy
- Member of the Danish Council on Climate Change
- Chairman of the Scientific Steering Committee for the scientific conference, CLIMATECHANGE: Global Risks, Challenges and Decisions
- Member of the **United Nations Scientific Panel** to draft the 2019 Global Sustainable Development Report
- Chair of the Scientific Steering Committee for the IARU hosted congress Global Challenges: Achieving Sustainability

Focus

Prominent figure in considerations of climate change and sustainability who has been influential in future thinking in the area of sustainable development, as well as having active involvement in related conferences and organizations.

TURENSCAPE

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
BEIJING, CHINA

Architecture Office

Focusing on Parks and Green Space in Cities
Planned and designed over 300 ecological cities and 1000 landscape projects in China

Founded by **Kongjian Yu**

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 6 - CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION, SDG 14 - LIFE BELOW WATER

Awards

- 2013 American Society of Landscape Architects (ASLA) Award
- 5 World's Best Landscape Awards at the World Architecture Festival.

Publications

- By Kongjian Yu:
Constructed Wetlands and Sustainable Development (2016)
- Art of Survival: Recovering Landscape Architecture* (2007)

Project

Qian'an Sanlihe River Ecological Corridor
The project has transformed an overly polluted landscape to a usable public space through diversions to clean and filter the water. A park for enjoyment of the area is able to be appreciated by local residents due to the use of creative climate adaptive solutions.

RAUMLABOR BERLIN

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
BERLIN, GERMANY

Architecture Firm

Focusing on Participatory Workshops and Spatial Interventions

Collective of Architects
Co-founded by
Andrea Hofman (left)

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Awards

2018 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture

2017 Curry Stone Design Prize for social design achievements

2017 Core77 Design Award

Publications

By Raumlabor:

Floating University Berlin 2018 - an illustrated report

Building the City Together

Art City Lab: New Spaces for Art

Project

Floating University:
A temporary floating structure in Berlin using resources carefully, and made to educate the public through workshops on water filtration and sustainable water use. The project combines architecture, artistic intervention, and climate education to encourage urban transformations, rethinking the environment.

AL BORDE

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
QUITO, ECUADOR

Architecture Firm

Focusing on sustainable public interest design

Founders:
Pascual Gangotena, David Barragán, Marialuisa Borja and Esteban Benavides

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

2019 100+ Best Architecture Firms DOMUS

2013 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture

Finalist - Refurbishment in Architecture Awards, House of the Flying Beds, ArchDaily

Exhibitions

2018 YALA - Young Architects in Latin America

2017 Triennale di Milano

2017 *Building with Optimism*, Carnegie Museum of Art

2014 *Think Global, Build Social! Architectures for a Better World*, Vienna

Project

New Hope School:
School constructed of local plant-fiber in Puerto Cabuyal Ecuador. Exemplary of incorporating scarcity into aesthetics while building for climate adaptation.

2018, Finalist FIBRA AWARD, World Prize for Contemporary Plant Fiber-Based Architecture

HOANG THUC HAO

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
HANOI, VIETNAM

**Architect, Engineer,
Educator, and Humanitarian**

Chairman and Lecturer for the
Architecture Association of
Hanoi University for Civil Engineering

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

- 2017 UIA Vassilis Sgoutas Prize
- 2016, 2017 Green Good Design Award
- 2016 Sia Gezt Prize
- 2016 Nominated for the Global Award for Sustainable Architecture
- 2015 Vietnamese Architect of the Year

Affiliations

Founder of the architecture firm 1+1>2, which focuses on supporting disadvantaged, rural communities

Executive member of the Association of Vietnamese Architects and the Green Architecture Council in Vietnam

Project

Sheltered Seedling House
Constructed from bamboo and plastic bottles in an area affected by HIV. The structure protects seedlings from climate conditions to further sustainable agriculture, but also provides farmers and children with a place to rest and meet. One of numerous projects such as community houses built with bamboo to provide assistance to disadvantaged communities.

CAROLA HEIN

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
DELFT, NETHERLANDS

**Architect and
Professor**

Chair and Professor of
History of Architecture and Urban Planning
at TU Delft
Focusing on tracing the history of oil
in relation to urbanism

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 13 - CLIMATE ACTION, SDG 6 - CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION

Publications

- Adaptive Strategies for Water Heritage* (2020)
- Planning History Handbook* (2018)
- Editor of *History, Urbanism, Resilience* (2016)

- Editor of *Port Cities: Dynamic Landscapes and Global Networks* (2011)
- "The Capital of Europe. Architecture and Urban Planning for the European Union" (2004)
- Rebuilding Urban Japan after 1945* (2003)

Project

Global Architecture of Oil:
Research into the use of oil as a resource and its inter-relationship with the built environment and landscape. The intent of the research is to understand the use of oil so that more energy efficient solutions to replace oil can be researched once oil dependence is thoroughly analyzed from an architectural perspective.

KUNLÉ ADEYEMI

REGION 5 - AFRICA
LAGOS, NIGERIA

Architect

Founder and principal of NLÉ architectural firm

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 14 - LIFE ON WATER, SDG 13 - CLIMATE ACTION

Awards

- 2016 Silver Lion prize at the Venice Biennale
- 2016 Aga Khan Award Shortlist

Affiliations

- 2017 Juror for Holcim Awards for Middle East Africa
- 2017 Aga Khan Design Critic in Architecture at Harvard University Graduate School of Design
- 2016 Juror RIBA international Prize
- 2014 Member of the International Advisory Council for the World Design Capital

Project

[African Water Cities, Makoko Floating School II & III](#): Project collaborating with the United Nations Development Program to design flood resilient, floating structures for coastal cities using locally sourced materials such as bamboo. The second and third prototype work on incorporating more resilient structures for diverse climate adaptation.

KOTCHAKORN VORAAKHOM

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
BANGKOK, THAILAND

Landscape Architect

Founded Porous City Network
Founded the Koungkuey Design Initiative (KDI)
Focuses on urban landscape design to fight the effects of flooding

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 6 - CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION, SDG 13 - CLIMATE ACTION, SDG 14 - LIFE BELOW WATER

Awards

- Echoing Green Climate Fellow
- Atlantic Fellow
- Asia Foundation Fellow
- TED Speaker on landscape design for climate change

Initiatives

Porous City Network - An initiative to rethink the design of urban planning to respond productively and sustainably to rain and floods and ensure better water resource management

Project

[Chulalongkorn Centenary Park](#): Urban park designed to store water during flooding, as well as filter water, prevent flooding, and allow green space to function as infrastructure in the city. The design also promotes sustainable vegetative growth and responsible water maintenance.

COOKING SECTIONS

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
LONDON, UK

Architects and Spatial Practitioners

Co-founded by Daniel Fernández Pascual and Alon Schwabe

Working at the intersection of architecture, visual art, and geopolitics by incorporating research with exhibition to explore the possibility of adapting food usage to climate

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Awards and Exhibitions

- 2019 Future Generation Art Prize
- 2019 nominated for the Visible Award
- 2014 exhibition at the U.S. Pavilion at the Venice Architecture Biennale

Research

Study of dry watering techniques allowing plant cultivation in dry conditions without irrigation.

Investigates flows of food and the intersection of landscape, architecture, and geopolitics.

Project

Climavore: On Tidal Zones project: An architectural intervention to make people more aware of the relationship between climate and their food sources which included meals taking place on sites according to the tides. The focus is on architecture as a driver for critical awareness of climate adaptation necessity, in relation to food and the environment.

MAIBRITT PEDERSEN ZARI

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
WELLINGTON, NEW ZEALAND

Architect, Educator, and Researcher

Senior Lecturer in Sustainable Architecture and Interior Architecture at Victoria University's School of Architecture, New Zealand

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 13 - CLIMATE ACTION, SDG 15 - LIFE ON LAND

Affiliations

Section leader and member of a multi-disciplinary team working on the Pacific Ecosystem-based Adaptation to Climate Change (PEBACC) project

Invited lead researcher of 'A Value Case for Regenerative Development' project for the New Zealand Ministry for the Environment

Publications

- Regenerative Urban Design and Ecosystem Biomimicry* (2018)
- "The Importance for Urban Biodiversity" (2018)
- Materials for a Healthy, Ecological and Sustainable Built Environment: Principles for Evaluation* (2017)

Focus

Her work focuses on re-thinking sustainability by researching biomimicry as a key component to innovation in sustainable design. Her research also includes ecosystem-based adaptation and design consideration to protect against repercussions of climate change.

GITA GOVEN

REGION 5 - AFRICA
CAPE TOWN, SOUTH AFRICA

Architect

Founder and CEO of ARG Design architecture firm

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT CITIES

Affiliations

Chair of the Sustainability Institute Board

Panel expert for Holcim workshop on Future Cities

Member of the advisory board for GreenCape

Member of the board of climate change think-tank process of the City of Cape Town and the African Centre for Cities

Awards

2007 CIA Award for Architecture from the Cape Institute for Architecture

2005 Holcim Middle East Africa Bronze Award

Project

Tsoga Environmental Center: Project to combine a community center with environmentally sustainable initiatives such as a recycling facility, a food garden, and a nursery. Constructed with sustainable, natural materials, climate adaptation technology such as rainwater harvesting, and designed to teach local people new skills.

MIKKEL K. KRAGH

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
ODENSE, DENMARK

Engineer, Professor, and Researcher

Head of Section/Professor, Department of Technology and Innovation at Syddansk Universitet

Focuses on developments in energy efficiency, resilience, and digitalization

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

Affiliations

Former head of BUILD Programme, Danish Architecture Centre

Member of the BLOXHUB Science Forum Advisory Board

Vice Chairman of Miljøforum Fyn - Byggeri - Advisory Board

Building Green - Advisory Board Member

Publications

"A Circular Metabolic Approach for Polycentric Cities"

"Exemplary Models of Innovation through Collaboration"

"Next-Generation curtain walling with vacuum insulation panels - Energy performance and design freedom."

Focus

Leader of a research team which focuses on the incorporation of digital methods to produce more sustainable building design with higher energy efficiency.

CHRIS LUEBKEMAN

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
SAN FRANCISCO, US

Architect and Global Director of Foresight/Research/Innovation at ARUP

Educated as a geologist, structural engineer, and architect. Frequent speaker on designing for a sustainable future.

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

drivers of change

Affiliations

Senior Fellow of the Design Futures Council

Member of the Urban Redevelopment Authority International Panel of Experts

Member of the Lee Kuan Yew World Prize Nominating Panel

Publications

Designing our Tomorrow (2015)

Drivers of Change (2009)

Project

Drivers of Change: identifies and explores 175 of the most important factors that will affect our world, arranged in a framework known as STEEP (Social, Technological, Economic, Environmental and Political)

DANNA MASAD

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
RAMALLAH, PALESTINE

Architect and Specialist in Earthen Construction

Designs green and socially conscious buildings and landscapes in Palestine

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/ PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Affiliations

Co-founder of Palestine's first green design firm ShamsArd, which specializes in natural building design using solar energy, wastewater recycling and regenerative landscaping

Research

Projects focus on the use of local and natural materials in ways to design climate friendly and adaptable buildings. An emphasis is placed on interaction with nature through landscape as well as responsible use of land and resources.

Project

Permaculture Training Center: A training center to learn about plants and vegetation. The construction includes a "geodesic dome, raised bed planters, spiral planters, vertical gardens, grey water reed beds, passive solar additions". The purpose of the building as well as its implementation work to adapt to climactic concerns through education and sustainable design.

EDWARD NG

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
HONG KONG

Architect, Professor, and Researcher

Professor of Architecture in the School of Architecture of The Chinese University of Hong Kong (CUHK)

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION/ PANEL 3: RESILIENT CITIES

Awards

International Award from RIBA

UNESCO Asia Pacific Heritage Jury Commendation for Innovation Award

2010 Red Cross Humanitarian Award

Affiliations

Associate Director of the Institute of Future Cities (IOFC)

Team Leader of Urban Sustainability and Public Health in the Institute of Environment, Energy and Sustainability (IEES)

Environmental consultant to the Government of the Hong Kong Special Administrative Region

Publications

Urban Climatic Map – an information tool for sustainable urban planning (2015)

Dense Cities in the Tropical Zone, in Solar Energy at Urban Scale (2012)

Designing High Density Cities – For Social and Environmental Sustainability (2009)

Focus

Ng specializes in green building, environmental and sustainable design, and urban climatology for city planning.

EAST COAST ARCHITECTS

REGION 5 - AFRICA
DURBAN, SOUTH AFRICA

Architecture Office Focusing on Social and Green Architecture

Directors:
Derek van Heerden
Steve Kinsler
Bartjan Hooft

PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

SDG 15 - LIFE ON LAND, SDG 6 - CLEAN WATER AND SANITATION, SDG 7 - AFFORDABLE CLEAN ENERGY

Awards

2016 Global Sustainability Award

2015 Architecture for Social Gain Award

2014 Honorable Mention For the Greenest School on Earth

2012 Afrisam SAIA Award for Sustainable Architecture

Project

Vele Secondary School:
The project uses a government school budget and incorporates rain harvesting technology, food gardens, solar energy, and green roofs in the construction of the school. Resources are used sparingly which reduces consumption as well as allows building within a strict budget.

**PANEL 2
DESIGN FOR
RETHINKING
RESOURCES**

RONALD RAEI

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
BERKELEY, US

Applied Architectural Researcher, Design Activist, and Professor

Acting Chair of the UC Berkeley Department of Architecture in the College of Environmental Design
Founder of Emerging Objects, which researches 3d printing technologies in building

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
PARIS, FRANCE

PAOLO CASCONI

Architect, Associate Professor, and Designer

Focusing on Digital Fabrication
Associate professor at the ENSA paris / Malaquais and at the Ecole Speciale d'Architecture of Paris
Founder of CoDesign Lab

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES / PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION, SDG 9 - INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Awards

Digital Practice Award of Excellence by the The Association for Computer Aided Design in Architecture (ACADIA)
2014 Emerging Voice Award by The Architectural League of New York.

Publications

Borderwall as Architecture: A Manifesto for the U.S.-Mexico Boundary
Printing Architecture: Innovative Recipes for 3D Printing
Earth Architecture
Ted Speaker on architecture and social justice

Project

Borderwall: Spatial intervention to re-think the border between the US and Mexico. Seesaws were designed on either side so citizens could play with those behind the wall. Rael is also an innovator in 3D printing research using earthen materials, and has printed full structures using technological innovations paired with natural materials.

Initiatives

Founded the Urban Fabrication Laboratory specialized in urban ecologies and digital fabrication
Primarily works in Cameroon and Burkina Faso utilizing digital fabrication methods with natural resources and educating others on their usage.

Research

Constructed a temporary Fab Lab in Marrakech for digital fabrication research
3D printed pavilion in Marrakech
Earth Playground, Burkina Faso, using natural materials to create an innovative play area

Project

African Fabbers School is a school which leads digital fabrication workshops in Cameroon as part of a network of European and African universities with the aim of sharing knowledge in new technologies for fabrication using innovative methods with local materials.

MAJD MASHHARAWI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
GAZA, PALESTINE

Engineer and Designer

Civil Engineer who is founder and CEO of GreenCake and SolarBox, which both use innovation in local material usage and design to problem solve in a region of resource scarcity due to conflict.

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards

2016 Winner of Japan Gaza Innovation Challenge

MIT Pan Arab competition prize

Selected as one of the most creative people in business by Fast Company

Ted Speaker on Responsible Material Usage

Initiatives

Founder and CEO of Sunbox, which designed an affordable, self-installable smart solar kit to combat electricity shortage in Gaza. Currently, Gaza's power grid currently provides only four consecutive hours of electricity.

Project

Green Cake
Design of a brick made of coal and wood ash that is stronger than an ordinary brick but weighs and costs half the price while also recycling materials from destroyed buildings. Due to the inability to get construction supplies across the border to Palestine, the innovation using local resources allows rebuilding to occur.

SUPERUSE STUDIOS

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
ROTTERDAM, NETHERLANDS

Architecture Firm

Co-founded by Césare Peeren (left)

Focuses on rethinking construction by emphasizing new possibilities for a circular building economy through innovative use of resources

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION, SDG 9 - INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Projects and Focus

A playground (above) designed using discarded wind blades from turbines. Starting from unwanted materials from other industries, waste is eliminated and circular systems are promoted through a new building supply-design model.

Publications

Superuse: Constructing New Architecture by Shortcutting Material Flows

Project

Superuse specializes in projects that eliminate waste and works to connect architects with those who are discarding materials through creation of the Harvest Map, which allows waste to find a useful place in the built environment through innovative design.

THOMAS LOMMÉE

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
BRUSSELS, BELGIUM

Designer and Artist

Co-founder of Infrastructures as well as **Open Structures Studio**, which focuses on innovating design solutions using a sustainable, modular system in order to minimize resource usage

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION, SDG 9 - INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Initiatives

OS Studio works to coordinate collaborative design processes, provide educational activities and open source design tools, as well as serving as consultants on modularity

The studio works to encourage the reformulation of design infrastructure systems in order to better incorporate sustainability as an embedded principle in systems of making.

Project

Open Structures Project: encourages a circular economy through the design of an open source modular construction system which allows pieces to be accessed and become interchangeable. Old parts can be reused through the innovation of connecting pieces. Participatory and individual construction is encouraged by the open system as well as the elimination of waste.

ANUPAMA KUNDOO

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
PUNE, INDIA

Architect

Focusing on sustainable, affordable design

Architect using material research to implement new, cost-effective methods of sustainable construction.

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2013 Arc Vision Women Architect of the Year, Honourable Mention
- 2003 Architect of the Year, Category Group Housing
- 2000 Architect of the Future, Indian Architect & Builder Award

Publications

- Sustainable Building Design Manual, Volume I & II*
- Sustainability and Globalization*
- Indian Architecture & Builder Urban Development*

Project

Volontariat Home for Homeless Children: Utilizes sustainable and affordable materials to construct a building for homeless children in Pondicherry India. Minimal consumption and innovative techniques allow the building to be constructed at a low cost making good design accessible to all.

CARLO RATTI

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
BOSTON, US

Architect, Engineer, and Professor

Professor at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Director of the MIT Senseable City Lab

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Affiliations

Delegate to the World Economic Forum
Member of the Italian Design Council
Former special adviser on Urban Innovation to the President and Commissioners of the European Commission

Publications

Waste is Information: Infrastructure Legibility and Governance (2017)
The City of Tomorrow: Sensors, Networks, Hackers, and the Future of Urban Life (2016)
Open Source Architecture (2015)
Decoding the City (2014)

Focus

Ratti's work deals with the built environment of cities – from street grids to plumbing and garbage systems – using sensors to change the ways we interact with and understand the city. An example of this is the project Trash Track, which tracks garbage using sensors to research disposal patterns.

STÉPHANIE CHALTIEL

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
LONDON, UK

Architect

Partner at MuDD Architects

Focuses on using local and natural materials in combination with technology. Current research focuses on the use of drones for quick, natural construction techniques.

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION, SDG 9 - INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE

Awards

2019, part of the ICON Design 100 talents
2019 Dezeen Awards Longlist
2017 ACADIA, MIT

Publications

"Light formwork for earthen monolithic shells" (2019)
"Adaptive Strategies for Mud Shell Robotic Fabrication" (2018)
"Monolithic Earthen Shells and Robotic Fabrication" (2017)

Project

Mud Shell, Drone Architecture: Research into Mud Spraying homes with drones to insulate buildings and to increase efficiency at time intensive tasks. She uses raw earth materials on simple wooden frames to quickly build structures from raw materials. The technique could be useful for future use after natural disasters for building emergency homes.

ANNE LACATON

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
PARIS, FRANCE

Architect and Professor

Professor at ETH in Zurich
Co-founder of Lacaton & Vassal

Works on sustainable housing projects as an advocate of building modestly and transforming existing structures

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

- 2018 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture
- 2016 LifeTime Achievement Award, Triennale de Arquitectura de Lisboa
- 2008 Grand Prix National de l'architecture

Affiliations

- Visiting professor at Harvard University, at the Superior Technical School of Architecture of Madrid and at the GSD Studio in Paris
- Held the Clarkson Chair in Architecture at the University at Buffalo. Innovation Panel

Project

Transformation of 530 Housing Units:
The project undertook the transformation of housing units using minimal materials and modifications in order to increase livability and efficiency. Particular attention is given to responsible consumption in choice and quantity of materials used.

MARTIN RAJNIS

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
PRAGUE, CZECH REPUBLIC

Architect

Co-founder of the Czech Chamber of Architects

Recognized for eco-construction, innovating design with wood

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards

- 2014 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture
- 2014 Architect of the Year in the Czech Republic

Affiliations

- Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Institute of Planning and Development of the City of Prague
- Former professor of architecture at the Academy of Arts, Architecture and Design in Prague

Focus

Rajnis employs innovative construction methods using wood in order to produce low cost building solutions from natural materials. His work exemplifies the ability to elevate vernacular materials through design innovation, while maintaining an ethos of sustainability.

DIÉBÉDO FRANCIS KÉRÉ

REGION 5 - AFRICA
OUAGADOUGOU, BURKINA FASO

Architect and Professor

Focuses on sustainable material usage

Professor of Architectural Design and Participation at the Technical University of Munich

Founder of the Berlin studio Kéré Architecture

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2017 Prince Claus Award
- 2012 Global Holcim Award
- 2009 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture
- 2004 Aga Khan Award for Architecture

Research

Past projects and focus has been on using local, affordable, and natural materials in innovative ways which are adaptive to climate. The outcomes are often socially beneficial buildings such as schools and libraries.

Project

Atelier Gando: Center being built in Burkina Faso for sustainable construction technologies and research, where indigenous building methods can be studied and innovative research rethinking resources can be undertaken. The building itself encourages the education of local architects, and shows innovations in material usage.

ALEXANDER BRODSKY

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
MOSCOW, RUSSIA

Architect and Artist

Russian architect focusing on creative ways to use salvaged and natural materials in construction, while concurrently creating artworks for exhibitions and participatory projects.

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards and Exhibitions

- 2010 - Kandinsky Russian Art Award
- 2010 Jardin des Tuileries Exposition
- 2006 Venice Biennale Russia Pavilion

Projects

Designer of one of the 16 bus stops in Krumbach commissioned to architects
Collaborative workshops constructing imaginary cities out of clay to demonstrate the potential of imagination to transform environment

Focus

Pavilion for Vodka Ceremonies is a structure designed to demonstrate the ability of salvaging locally found materials (old window frames) to create traditional, aesthetically pleasing, and memory-inducing architecture. Other temporary structures such as the Ice House, made of ice cubes, demonstrate creative ways to rethink resources.

SALTO ARCHITECTS

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
TALLINN, ESTONIA

Architecture Firm

Founded by
Maarja Kask and
Ralf Lööke

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards

2018 Best Building of
the Year in Tartu

2011 World Architecture
Festival: Highly com-
mended in Culture Cate-
gory

2010 The Annual Award
of the Union of Esto-
nian Landscape Archi-
tects

2010 Wooden Building of
the Year in Estonia: Best
Facade

Project

Straw Theater:
An award winning project
reactivating an abandoned
location by using natural
materials for building. The
purpose was to show straw
as a viable renewable materi-
al for building a public
theater, as well as to utilize
the potential in existing build-
ings to be transformed, giving
new life to the city.

DAVID BENJAMIN

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
NEW YORK, US

Architect and Associate Professor

Associate Professor at
Columbia Graduate School of Architecture

Founder of The Living
Focusing on the intersection of biology,
computation, and design

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 9 - INNOVATION AND INFRASTRUCTURE, SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards

Emerging Voices Award
from the Architectural
League

Holcim Sustainability
Award

The Young Architects
Program Award from the
Museum of Modern Art
and MoMA PS1

Research

Benjamin's work with
The Living focuses on
research relating biology,
computation, and sus-
tainability to find
innovative ideas for
architecture.

Project

Hy-fi Mushroom Bricks:
Tower made of organically
grown bricks from
mushrooms which were
molded. Exemplary of the
ability to use biology and
technology to produce
sustainable and innovative
solutions for design.

EKO PRAWOTO

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
YOGYAKARTA, INDONESIA

Architect and Educator

Teaches at the Duta Wacana University in Yogyakarta, specializing in innovative uses of bamboo for affordable design solutions

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

2010 Aga Khan Award Shortlist

Focus

Prawoto focuses on pushing the limits of what can be done with readily available natural resources such as bamboo. His contribution to the 2013 Singapore Biennale (top left) demonstrates his aesthetic construction methods with simple materials and traditional building methods. He has been recognized for applying these solutions to humanitarian efforts.

Project

Ngibikan Village Reconstruction: After the 2006 earthquake affordable techniques for reconstruction using bamboo and other durable natural materials were implemented concurrently with participatory approaches so that the community could quickly and affordably rebuild with a high degree of self-sufficiency. Innovations in material usage made reconstruction possible.

COMUNAL TALLER

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
MEXICO CITY, MEXICO

Architectural Studio

Focusing on education and participatory design coupled with innovative techniques in local material usage.

Founded by
Mariana Ordóñez Grajales (left)

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Awards

2018 Emerging Voices Award from the Architectural League of New York

Marielle France Community Design Award

Initiatives

Comunal focuses on architecture as a participatory practice, and has completed numerous projects in rural communities of Mexico where education is key to the implementation. Work focuses on social justice, equality, and access to health and other necessary resources.

Project

Social Production of Housing: Project educating a community on how to utilize local and easily accessible natural materials such as bamboo in order to build housing and public buildings such as schools. The focus was on construction workshops and participatory design to ensure a sustainable future in building with local resources after the architects had left.

BILLIE FAIRCLOTH

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
PHILADELPHIA, US

Architect, Researcher, and Professor

Professor and Lecturer at Harvard, as well as KADK, the University of Texas, and the University of Pennsylvania

Research Director and Partner at KieranTimberlake

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES /
PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

Awards

2016 Architect Magazine R+D Award

2014 AIA Building Information Modeling Award

2013 Architect Magazine R+D Award, Green Roof Vegetative Survey

2013 Architect Magazine R+D Award

Publications

Building Research Practices: Connecting Education and Practice Through Architectural Research (2019)

Plastics Now: On Architecture's Relationship to a Continuously Emerging Material (2015)

"Quantifying the Embodied Environmental Impact of Building Materials During Design: A Building Information Modeling Based Methodology,"

Focus

Her work seeks to investigate why architects build using the current methods and practices. She works developing technology for data gathering in the built environment in order to maximum the performance of design and gather information on building usage.

BOONSERM PREMTHADA

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
BANGKOK, THAILAND

Architect

Specializing in the use of local, handcrafted materials

Founder of Bangkok Project Studio

PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

SDG 12 - RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION

Awards

2018 Global Sustainability Award

Silpathorn Award for Creative Design: Architectural Design

2011 ar+d Awards for Emerging Architecture

2013 Shortlist Aga Khan Award for Architecture

2012 Shortlist Brick Award

2012 Highly commended World Architecture Festival

Project

Kantana Institute: Project which extended the life of brick and succeeded in saving a local brick company. Local handmade bricks were used. The project proves the ability to transform a traditional material with innovative design and construction methods, while supporting local communities through material choice.

**PANEL 3
DESIGN FOR
RESILIENT COMMUNITIES**

NATALIA FISHMAN-BEKMAMBETOVA

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
KAZAN, RUSSIA

Architect and Urban Planner

Assistant to the President of the Republic of Tatarstan

City architect of Tatarstan focusing on a public development program for parks and green space

ALEJANDRO ECHEVERRI

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
MEDELLÍN, COLOMBIA

Architect, Urban Planner, and Educator

Co-founder and Director of URBAM, the Center for Urban and Environmental Studies at EAFIT University in Medellín, Colombia

Founder of the design studio, Alejandro Echeverri + Valencia Arquitectos

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

2019 Aga Khan Award for the Development of Public Spaces in Tatarstan

Affiliations

Coordinated educational programmes for the Strelka Institute for Media, Architecture and Design

Served as Counsellor to the Head of the Department of Culture of the Government of Moscow

Project

The Institute for Urban Development of the Republic of Tatarstan has been implementing a Program for the Development of Public Spaces, which includes improvements by constructing more than 300 parks, embankments, pedestrian streets, public gardens and squares in all municipal districts of the region.

Awards

2013 Veronica Rudge Green Prize in Urban Design from Harvard

2009 Curry Stone Prize

2008 Pan-American Biennale in Urban Design Award

1996 Colombian National Architectural Award

Initiatives

Co-author of Laufen Manifesto, written as a call for socially-oriented design

Responsible for a number of projects constructing libraries, parks (such as Parque Explora shown above), schools, and community centers in Medellín.

Research

Co-investigator on the project Transitional Cities In The Global South And Their Contribution To Sdg Implementation: Governance And Power Relations In Medellín working to research successful bottom-up approaches to achieving the UN SDG goal for sustainable cities in the Global South.

JANA REVEDIN

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
PARIS, FRANCE

Architect, Professor, Theorist, and Writer

Professor of Architecture and Urban planning at École Spéciale d'Architecture in Paris

**PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE**

Affiliations

Created the Global Award for Sustainability in Architecture

Member of the LAURE research laboratory 'Environment, city, society'

UNESCO delegate to the Education and Research Commission of the UIA

Publications

Sustainable Design I-V: Towards a New Ethics for Architecture and the City

"The Radicant City: Why Sustainable Living Space grows Like Ivy"

The Eleven Books on Architecture: Design Theories for Societies in Change

Focus

Creator of the Global Award for Sustainable Architecture as well as professor and author of numerous books, focusing on sustainable design and the city as a sustainable space for growth. She encourages participatory and experimental methods for achieving the SDGs.

EMANUEL ADMASSU

REGION 5 - AFRICA
ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA

Architect, Assistant Professor, and Artist

Assistant Professor at RISD
Ethiopian born architect who is a founding partner of AD-WO in the US

Focusing on global inequalities studied through market development in Africa

**PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY**

Exhibitions

South of the Sahara: Accelerated Urbanism in Africa, Tel Aviv Museum of Art

Video Studio: Meeting Points, Studio Museum in Harlem

Affiliations

Panelist at the Africa Development Conference

Collaborator on Columbia University's African Mobilities Project

Project

Two Markets Project: Examines two marketplaces - one in Addis Ababa and one in Dar es Salaam - to understand the intersection of individual narratives with space and economy. The resulting research is used by Admassu in an exhibition context (above) to incite dialogue about colonialism and global developmental inequality.

ANNA RUBBO

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
NEW YORK, US

Architect and Researcher

Research Scholar at the Center for Sustainable Urban Development at Columbia University's Earth Institute

Co-founder and editor of the journal *Architectural Theory Review* (1996-2010)

YOUNG JOON KIM

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
SEOUL, KOREA

Architect, Urban Planner, and Professor

City Architect of Seoul

Focusing on urban planning projects to encourage sustainable urban growth.

Founder of Yo2 Architects

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Affiliations

Previously Associate Professor in Architecture, University of Sydney

Former member of the UN Millennium Project Task Force on Improving the Lives of Slum Dwellers (2002-2004)

Awards

2014 UIA Vassilis Sgoutas Prize mention for humanitarian work in education

2011 Australian AIA Neville Quarry Education Award

2010 Life Fellowship of the AIA

2006 Marion Mahony Griffin award

Publications

'They Don't Listen: Urban Education, the Professions and the Urban Poor' (2019)

City Maker Survey Working Paper (2019)

Inclusive Urbanization (2014)

'Design as Engaged Practice' (2012)

Project

Global Studio:
An international 'think and do tank' that encouraged design students and professional to 'partner' with the urban poor, so they might work more effectively with underserved communities, and contribute to realizing the SDGs. She has also published widely on developmental issues and women and development in Colombia.

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Affiliations

Professor at MIT and Seoul National University

Curator of the Seoul Biennale

Coordinator of Paju Book City in South Korea

Publications

Urbanism for Architecture

Project

Sewoon Sangga:
Led the project for a collaboration with 60 architects to transform a condemned building in Seoul. The original building was an old shopping complex, which through thoughtful transformation was restored minimally and made into a creative hub for local businesses and startups.

RUTA LEITANAITE

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
VILNIUS, LITHUANIA

Architect and Curator

Director of the Architects Association of Lithuania

JUAN DU

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
HONG KONG

Architect, Associate Professor, and Researcher

Specializing in affordable urban housing

Associate Dean and Associate Professor at the Faculty of Architecture at the University of Hong Kong

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Affiliations

Board Member of A10 Coop, an architectural cooperative working on issues of art, politics, economy, and society

On the Rio2020 UIA Congress Scientific Committee

Publications

Vilnius 1900-2016. A Guide to City's Architecture (2016)

Architecture: Farewell Iconic, Hello Humane (2011)

Focus

Actively involved on projects that focus on the future of the built environment in an urban context, urban planning projects in Vilnius, as well as curator and organizer of numerous architectural events.

Affiliations

Curator of *Housing an Affordable City* Exhibition at the 2011 Shenzhen Hong Kong Bi-City Biennale

Previously taught at MIT

Frequent invited speaker at events such as the Holcim Forum for Sustainable Construction in Shanghai

Publications

The Shenzhen Experiment: The Story of China's Instant City (2020)

"Beyond Classification", *E-flux* (2018)

City Metamorphosis: Shenzhen Caiwuwei Research (2013)

Over 20 Academic Publications

Project

Runs HKU Urban Ecologies of Affordable Housing Studio: Research is on design to create new low cost social housing solutions in cities but also on the future of rapid urbanization and urban planning.

ALFRED OMENYA

REGION 5 - AFRICA
NAIROBI, KENYA

Environmental Architect and Professor

Associate Professor at the University of Nairobi

Founder and Principal Researcher of Eco Build Africa

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Affiliations

Held research consultancies for many international organizations: the World Bank, UN-Habitat, UNEP, African Union, Sida (Sweden), UK-Aid, Oxfam GB, GOAL Ireland

Collaborates in research with Harvard Graduate School, ETH Zurich, University of Manchester, University of Florida

Publications

“Network analysis as an alternative tool for understanding and intervening in informal housing: case studies from Nairobi, Kenya”

“Agent-based modelling of urban sanitation: informal settlements in Nairobi”

Published over 70 academic papers

Project

Collaborated with Sweden on the SymbioCity Kenya Program to further sustainable city growth and improve quality of life. The program consists of pilot programs in small cities throughout Kenya in order to build coalitions to communicate about the needs of growing cities.

GERHARD SCHMITT

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
ZURICH, SWITZERLAND

Architect and Professor

Professor of Information Architecture at ETH Zurich and leader of the ETH Future Cities Laboratory Simulation Platform

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Affiliations

Founding Director of the Singapore-ETH Centre in Singapore

ETH Zurich Senior Vice President for ETH Global

Vice President for Planning and Logistics and Member of the Board of ETH Zurich

Publications

“Urban Autopoiesis: Towards Adaptive Future Cities”

“Cognitive Computing for Urban Design”

“Visualizing Future Cities”

“How To Create Sustainable, Pulsating Cities of the Future”

Focus

His research, focuses on smart cities and linking big data to urban design using AI and computer aided design to implement innovative research methods speculating on sustainable futures of cities.

OLGA ALEKSAKOVA

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
MOSCOW, RUSSIA

Architect and Professor

Professor of Architecture at
Moscow Architecture School

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

Archsovet Award
for the best public
building of 2017

Affiliations

Co-founder of
Buromoscow
architecture
firm

Previously supervisor
of Strelka Institute
Research Program on
Energy

Project

Kindergarten Vrshavskoe:
Urban planning project by
Buromoscow which focused
on cost efficient solutions
to building a kindergarten
focusing on well-being of the
children incorporating
innovative spaces to learn
through good design. Low
cost and innovative design
solutions are critical for
sustainable development in
urban environments.

MARTHA THORNE

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
MADRID, SPAIN

Architect, Author, and Theorist

Dean of IE University's
Madrid and Segovia
School of Architecture and Design

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES /
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Affiliations

Executive Director of the
Pritzker Architecture Prize

Former Associate
Curator for the
Department of Architecture
at The Art Institute of
Chicago

Serves on an international
jury for the award,
ArcVision: Women and
Architecture

Publications

*Masterpieces of Chicago Ar-
chitecture and Skyscrapers:
The New Millennium*

Editor and author for *The
Pritzker Architecture Prize:
The First Twenty Years*

Author of numerous articles
for architectural journals
and encyclopedias

Ted Speaker on what makes
a city livable

Focus

Focuses on evolution
and changes
in architecture as well as
progress in cities and the
relationship to architecture.
She is a frequent
speaker on the topic of
sustainable futures.

YAŞAR ADNAN ADANALI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
ISTANBUL, TURKEY

**Urban Planner,
Researcher,
and Lecturer**

Director and Co-founder of the
Center for Spatial Justice

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Affiliations

Worked as development specialist for Stuttgart University on refugee camp improvement projects of United Nations Relief and Works Agency for the Palestine Refugees (UNRWA)

Teaches participatory planning courses at TU Darmstadt

Member of One Hope Association and Düzce Hope Studio

Founder of the Center for Spatial Justice in Istanbul

Published *Spatial Justice and Children* to highlight the needs of children in cities

Project

Center for Spatial Justice
Development in urban environments is facilitated by organizing participatory community-oriented planning workshops with the intended outcome to make the development process more equitable in urban planning. Transnational knowledge is brought to local impoverished communities to encourage change.

HSIEH YING-CHUN

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
TAIPEI, TAIWAN

**Architect and
Humanitarian**

Known for dedicating his career to work focusing on rebuilding more resilient homes in small communities in Taiwan and China after earthquakes and other natural disasters

**PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY**

Affiliations

Founder of Atelier 3 and Rural Architecture Studio

Member of the architectural team WEAK! which operates Ruin Academy, an independent architectural research center

Awards

2012 Golden Prize of the Shenzhen Affordable Housing Design Competition (China)

2012 16th National Awards for Arts (Taiwan)

2011 Curry Stone Design Prize

2004 shortlisted for UN-HABITAT's Best Practice Award

Project

Reconstruction after Taiwan's flood:
Reconstruction of homes after the flood which took into account both sustainable building practices as well as lowering cost of construction. Since the 1990's he has dedicated all of his efforts to similar practices creating resilient communities and rebuilding after natural disasters in Taiwan and China.

ELISABETE FRANÇA

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
SÃO PAULO, BRAZIL

Architect, Professor, and Urban Planner

Project and Planning Superintendent of the Traffic Engineering Company of the city of São Paulo

Professor of Architecture and Urbanism at the Armando Álvares Penteado College (FAAP)

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Affiliations

Coordinator of projects linked to the World Bank, Inter-American Development Bank and UN-Habitat

Former Director of Planning and Projects of São Paulo State Housing and Urban Development Company

On the Rio2020 UIA Congress Scientific Committee

Awards

2012 UN-Habitat Scroll of Honors Award

Focus

Coordinator of many urban development projects which focused on revitalizing low income areas and solving housing issues related to socio-economic status and sustainable urban growth.

PETER MOULD

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
SYDNEY, AUSTRALIA

Architect

Previously NSW Government Architect from 2006 to 2012

Adjunct Professor at the Faculty of the Built Environment, University of New South Wales.

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Affiliations

Member of the City of Sydney Design Advisory Panel

Member of the Victorian Design Review Panel

Member of the South Australian Design Review Panel

On the Metropolitan Redevelopment Authority Design Panel

UIA 17 Scientific Committee Member

Served on NSW Heritage Council and chaired its Approvals Committee,

Was Deputy President of the NSW Architects Registration Board

Previously a Councillor for the UIA

Focus

Expert and author on Islamic architecture regularly serving on scientific committees and a member of numerous panels. His interests are focused on urban design and adaptive reuse.

BIGE TUNÇER

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
SINGAPORE

Architect and Professor

Associate professor of Architecture and Sustainable Design at Singapore University of Technology and Design (SUTD)

ZEGEYE CHERENET MAMO

REGION 5 - AFRICA
ADDIS ABABA, ETHIOPIA

Architect, Assistant Professor, and Urban Planner

Head of the Competence Center of Architecture and Design at EiABC and Acting Head of Emerging City Lab-AA.

Assistant Professor at the Ethiopian Institute of Architecture, at Addis Ababa University (EiABC)

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

SDG 11 - SUSTAINABLE CITIES

Initiatives

Regularly leads scientific workshops and gives lectures internationally

Member of scientific committees of various journals and conferences

Organized two international peer-reviewed conferences

Research

Leads a large multi-disciplinary research project, granted from the Sustainable Urban Living program of the Ministry of National Development Research Fund of Singapore

Researcher for the Future Cities Laboratory at ETH Zurich

Focus

Prominent figure in re-thinking sustainable urban development in Asia and frequent speaker on sustainable design.

Affiliations

Served as the general secretary of the Association of Ethiopian Architects

Holcim jury member for Middle East Africa

Deputy scientific director of EiABC

Guest at the Department of Architecture at ETH Zurich

Publications

Building Ethiopia: Sustainability and Innovation in Architecture and Design (2012)

UN Chronicle article: "The Demand for Responsive Architectural Planning and Production in Rapidly Urbanizing Regions: the Case of Ethiopia"

Project

Ethiopia's Newtown Project: collaborator and consultant on urban planning for a project to turn rural villages into urban centers by creating self-sustaining towns, maintaining regional agricultural practices and ways of life, but introducing urban skill sets.

**PANEL 4
DESIGN FOR
HEALTH**

CHRISTIAN BENIMANA

REGION 5 - AFRICA
KIGALI, RWANDA

Architect

Co-founder of the African Design Centre to empower leaders to design a more sustainable future

Program Manager of MASS Design Group, which researches and builds architecture focusing on social justice issues

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Affiliations

Chairman of the Education Board of the Rwanda Institute of Architects

Chairman of the Education Board of the East African Institute of Architects

Taught at the architecture school of the former Kigali Institute of Science and Technology (KIST)

Focus

Worked on the Liberia Health Infrastructure Standards and Guidelines for the Ministry of Health and Social Welfare

Worked on the master plan for the Albert Schweitzer hospital in Lambarene, Gabon

Project

Maternity Waiting Village project in Malawi:
The project involved constructing a building to help lower infant and maternity mortality rates by creating a center where women could gather in the last month of pregnancy to cook, socialize, and receive care. The design of the building was made to foster better health and well-being.

RICCARDO VANNUCCI

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
ROME, ITALY

Architect and Researcher

Co-Founder of FARE studio

Focuses on the design of sustainable development projects in lower income communities globally

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Awards

2014 Rotthier European Architecture Special Prize

2010 Zumtobel Group Award for Sustainability and Humanity the Philippe

2010 shortlisted for the Aga Khan Award

2008 Health Category Award at the World Architecture Festival

Affiliations

Senior Scientist in the Laboratory of Construction and Architecture at École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)

Ongoing working relationship with UN's Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)

Project

Centre pour le Bien-être des Femmes in Ouagadougou Burkina Faso
Project working to provide health and educational services and raises awareness of women's rights in an atmosphere where female genital mutilation is common. The building uses passive cooling and also serves as a community meeting center.

DOREEN ADENGO

REGION 5 - AFRICA
KAMPALA, UGANDA

**Architect, Curator,
and Educator**

Head of Adengo Architecture

Specializes in innovative collaboration
across disciplines

LINE RAMSTAD

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
OSLO, NORWAY

**Architect and
Humanitarian**

Founded the nonprofit architecture
organization Gyaw Gyaw
working in Asia

**PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE**

**PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE**

Exhibitions

2018 Kampala Art Biennale

African Mobilities:
Kampala Exchange
Workshop and
Exhibition

Affiliations

Member of the Steering
Committee for the 2017
African Architecture Awards

Lecturer at the New School,
Pratt Institute, and the
University of Johannesburg's
Graduate School of
Architecture

Collaborator on Columbia
University's African Mobilities
project

Projects

Adengo Architecture
specializes in collaborative
projects in Uganda, including
the African Mobilities Project
raising awareness of issues
for refugees in Kampala.

Other projects include a
school, vocational camp, and
Mobile Medical Camp (above)
using renewable energy to
provide access to healthcare
in rural areas of Uganda.

Awards

2016 Terra Award
Shortlist for
Earthen
Architecture

Focus

Gyaw Gyaw focuses
on community
oriented buildings in
remote parts of
Thailand, such as
school and health
clinics, taking into
account the needs
of the community
through a
participatory process.

Project

Mae Tao Clinic Training
Center

In a remote region of Thailand
near the border of Burma, a
project was undertaken to add
on to the Mae Tao Clinic to fa-
cilitate the training of medical
staff. Along with educating
new medics, migrant schools
for children are run as well.

The building uses healthy
techniques as well as natural
resources such as adobe.

PETER WILLIAMS

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
NEW YORK, US

Architect

Founder and Executive Director of Architecture for Health in Vulnerable Environments (ARCHIVE) Global

Working to address problems of health through design and construction of affordable health-promoting housing.

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Awards

- 2013 Katerva Award for Sustainability
- 40 under 40' Leader in International Development
- 2011 Utne Reade, one of "25 People Who Are Changing the World"

Affiliations

- Former Consultant and International Strategy Advisor for the World Bank
- President/CEO of the International Institute of Rural Construction

Project

Malaria Prevention Building in Cameroon
Project to combat malaria in Cameroon through preventative building design, including mosquito nets in ceilings, ventilation adjustments, and improving sewage and water systems. Careful consideration of the needs of at-risk communities works to lower the spread of disease.

ORKID STUDIO

REGION 5 - AFRICA
NAIROBI, KENYA

Architecture Studio

Architecture Studio in Kenya working across Africa

Co-founded by:
Tatu Gatere (left)
and James Mitchell

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Initiatives

- Specializes in health clinics and hospital building as well as other social/public buildings, focusing on well being of the inhabitants
- Penda Health Clinics: Project to adapt existing buildings to be functional health centers.
- Sachibondu Hospital: restored an existing hospital for thousands of isolated rural residents with no nearby health facilities to have better lighting, ventilation, as well as specialized areas for treatment of infectious disease and operations.

Project

Nakuru children's home:
Uses earthbag construction, natural insulation methods, and rainwater collection to create a low cost home for children using local materials. The building considers light and adds private sleeping arrangements to allow the children's home to provide a better quality of living than a typical children's home in Africa.

ARIF HASAN

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
KARACHI, PAKISTAN

Architect, Lecturer, and Urban Planner

Recognized for his work focusing on sustainable development solutions in informal settlements of Karachi to encourage better health and access to necessary facilities

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2003 Life Time Achievement Award of the Institute of Architects Pakistan
- 2001 Hilal-e-Imtiaz for Public Service of the Government of Pakistan
- 2000 Prince Claus Award for contribution to architecture and development

Affiliations

- Member of UN's Advisory Group on Forced Evictions
- Chairperson, Orangi Pilot Project-Research & Training Institute
- Chairperson, Urban Resource Centre, Karachi
- Member of the Steering Committee of the Aga Khan Award for Architecture (1990-1996)

Publications

- "Global Capital and the Cities of the South"
- "Pragmatism and the Built Environment"
- "Squatter Settlements in Karachi"
- Understanding Karachi: Planning and Reform for the Future* (2002)

Project

Orangi Pilot Project
Project to improve a low income housing area in order to encourage sustainable development by providing innovative access to sanitation (self designed, installed, and managed systems) as well as health and education revisions, including a health program for disease prevention. All of which contributed to lower instances of disease.

ROZANA MONTIEL

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
MEXICO CITY, MEXICO

Architect and Social Justice Advocate

Founder of Rozana Montiel Estudio de Arquitectura

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2019 The Sustainable Global Award for Architecture
- Moira Gemmill Award for Emerging Architecture
- Holcim Foundation for Sustainable Construction Grant

Publications

HU: Common Spaces in Housing Units

Project

Court:
A sports complex and community center designed for a housing complex to incorporate a variety of physical activities. Vegetation and plants are utilized to naturally cool the area. Outdoor activity is encouraged through thoughtful spatial planning.

SIERRA BAINBRIDGE

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
BOSTON, US

Architect, Educator, and Director of MASS

Senior Principal and
Managing Director of
MASS Design Group

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Awards

MASS has been named finalist for the TED Prize, Aga Khan Award, and Buckminster Fuller Challenge.

Affiliations

Consultant for USAID on climate change resiliency.
Former Head of the Architecture Department at the Kigali Institute of Science and Technology (KIST)
Taught at the University of Pennsylvania and the GSD
Visiting critic at Cornell, MIT, and MICA

Project

Butaro District Hospital Rwanda:
A hospital designed in an under-served region of Rwanda with design considerations focusing on maternal services as well as design to reduce the transmission of airborne disease and use of local volcanic rock to sustainably construct the building itself.

CHRISTOPHER WEBSTER

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
HONG KONG

Architect and Professor

Dean of the Faculty of Architecture at the University of Hong Kong and Chair Professor in Urban Planning and Development Economics

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Affiliations

Leader of the Healthy High Density Cities Lab at HKU
Research output from Sustainable and High Density City, merges Engineering, Medicine and Architecture

Publications

Healthy Cities: Public Health through Urban Planning
China's Urban Poverty
Editor of *Private Cities: local and Global Perspectives*

Project

Producing food and enhancing community in the city: A research initiative using a hybrid design-land economy approach to investigate the barriers to urban farming in Hong Kong so that they may be corrected and new options may be explored further.

DK OSSEO-ASARE

REGION 5 - AFRICA
TEMA, GHANA

**Architect,
Assistant Professor,
and Designer**

Co-Founder of Low Design Office (LOWDO), based in Ghana

Assistant Professor of Architecture and Engineering Design at Penn State University

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 8 - DECENT WORK AND ECONOMIC GROWTH

Awards

Rockefeller Foundation's Centennial Innovation Challenge Award

Design Corps' 2017 SEED Award for Public Interest Design

Ted Global Fellow

Initiatives

Runs the Penn State Humanitarian Materials Lab (HuMatLab)

Associate Director of Penn State's Alliance for Education, Science, Engineering and Design with Africa (AESEDA)

Led urban design for the Koumbi City and Anam City new town projects in Ghana and Nigeria

Project

Co-founder of Agbogbloshie Makerspace Platform (AMP Spacecraft): A community project with open architecture to ensure a safe and accessible space for crafting from e-waste in Africa. The structures are replicable and mobile. Health risks are minimized by designing for a safe working environment.

AMALE ANDRAOS

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
NEW YORK, US

Architect and Dean of the Columbia Graduate School of Architecture

Co-founder of WORKac

Focuses on architectural projects reinventing the relationship between urban and natural environments

PANEL 4: DESIGN FOR HEALTH

SDG 3 - GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

Affiliations

Board member for the Architectural League of New York

Board member of the Arab Center for Architecture

Publications

49 Cities, a re-reading of 49 visionary plans through an ecological lens

Eco-visionaries: Art, Architecture, and New Media After the Anthropocene exhibition book

Project

Public Farm: A completely off-grid, biodegradable and recyclable half-acre urban farm that also serves as an outdoor social space for education, play, and community building in New York City. Design is thoughtfully considered to allow access to and education about healthy food.

**PANEL 5
DESIGN FOR
INCLUSIVITY**

MARIAM KAMARA

REGION 5 - AFRICA
NIAMEY, NIGER

Architect and Associate Professor

Associate Professor of Urban Studies at Brown University

Founder of the architecture and research firm Atelier Masōmī in Niamey

SUAD AMIRY

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
RAMALLAH, PALESTINE

Architect, Author, and Educator

Director and Founder of the Riwaq Centre for Architectural Conservation, the first to work on rehabilitation of architectural heritage in Palestine

Visiting lecturer at numerous universities

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

Rockefeller Foundation's Centennial Innovation Challenge award

2018 Silver global LafargeHolcim award

2017 Architect Magazine R+D Award

2017 Regional LafargeHolcim Award

Affiliations

Founding member of united4design, a global collective of architects working on projects in the U.S., Afghanistan and Niger including a UN Habitat project

Head of the LafargeHolcim Awards jury for Middle East Africa in 2020

Project

Dandaji Cultural Complex: Restored a historical but rundown mosque to a library and cultural center which could be used inclusively by all. Women were previously unable to use the mosque, but now are invited to use the library and to business classes held in the community center.

Awards

2013 Aga Khan Award for Architecture for the Revitalization of Birzeit Historic Centre

2004 Viareggio Prize

Publications

Peasant Architecture in Palestine: Space, Kinship and Gender (2018)

Nothing to Lose But Your Life: an 18 hour Journey with Murad

Project

Revitalization of Birzeit Historic Center: The intention of the project was to preserve Palestine's cultural heritage. Conservation interventions were initiated to promote future development and create local jobs, while simultaneously reducing poverty through restoration of the built environment.

ALFREDO BRILLEMBOURG

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
CARACAS, VENEZUELA

Urban Designer and Professor

Co-founder of Urban-Think Tank (U-TT) in Caracas, Venezuela working to create initiatives of participatory and inclusive urban development

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

- 2012 Holcim Global Silver Award
- 2012 Venice Biennale of Architecture Golden Lion
- 2011 Holcim Gold Award for Latin America
- 2010 Ralph Erskine Award

Affiliations

Co-founded the Sustainable Living Urban Model Laboratory (S.L.U.M. Lab) at Columbia University

Former co-chair of Architecture and Urban Design at the Swiss Institute of Technology (ETH) in Zurich

Project

Caracas Metrocable Project: Infrastructural initiative by Urban Think Tank to construct a metro cable to connect the informal settlement of San Agustin to other neighborhoods in the city. The initiative used a community planning approach to make transportation accessible to often excluded residents of the city.

YASMEEN LARI

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
KARACHI, PAKISTAN

Architect and Social Justice Advocate

Pakistan's first female architect known as an advocate for social justice

Executive Director and founder of the humanitarian NGO Heritage Foundation Pakistan

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

- 2016 Fukuoka Prize for Arts and Culture
- 2011 Pakistani "1st Wonder Women of the Year Award"
- 2002 U.N. Recognition Award for efforts and results to promote cultural and historical conservation

Affiliations

Former UNESCO National Director

Former President of the Institute of Architects Pakistan

Member of UNESCO Consultative Committee for Moenjodaro

Elected Member of RIBA

Trustee of Transparency International Pakistan

Focus

Lari's work focuses on cultural preservation of Pakistani heritage, but she has also done numerous humanitarian projects such as rebuilding after the 2005 earthquake and designing disaster resilient structures using natural and local materials combined with traditional building methods. She is widely regarded as a humanitarian and social justice advocate.

ASIYE ETAFULENI

REGION 5 - AFRICA
DURBAN, SOUTH AFRICA

NGO focusing on Urban Planning

Works to support local economies of traders who use public spaces to sell goods, offering design expertise to ensure informal traders are included in economic development

Co-founded by Richard Dobson and Patrick Ndlovu

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

2014 Diakonia Human Rights Award for advancing the rights of informal workers

Curry Stone Social Design Circle Honoree

Initiatives

Innecity Cardboard Recycling Project

Infrastructural Upgrading Projects in the herb market and bead market

Working in Warwick - a book detailing narratives of traders and their involvement in economic development and urban policy

Project

Warwick Junction: Project which includes developing of infrastructure in Warwick Junction, a major transportation hub in Durban - to support informal traders by consultation on spatial use, spatial upgrades, as well as a recycling project. The initiative works to ensure inclusive economic development in the city.

FLORA SAMUEL

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
READING, UK

Architect and Professor

Professor of Architecture in the Built Environment at the University of Reading and Urban Living Research Group Lead

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Affiliations

RIBA Vice President Research

RIBA Elected National Councillor

Member of Academy of Urbanism

Member of Hong Kong Research Council, Architects' Council of Europe Innovation Panel.

Publications

Why Architects Matter: Evidencing and Communicating the Value of Architects (2018)

Le Corbusier: Architect and Feminist (2004)

Nature and Space: Aalto and Le Corbusier (2002)

Focus

Research, publications, and activities focus on social responsibility of architects to implement change. Particular focus is paid to the potential role of architects in housing solutions.

MARWA AL-SABOUNI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
HOMS, SYRIA

Architect and Urban Thinker

Runs the Arabic Gate for architectural news, the only online media outlet dedicated to architectural news in Arabic

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY / PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

Prince Claus Award for proposal to restore cooperation, social cohesion, and a sense of identity in Syria

Publications

The Battle for Home: The Vision of a Young Architect in Syria

TED speaker on the intersection of war and architecture in Syria

Project

Proposals for rebuilding the Baba Amr district of Homs:

The project focused on developing alternative solutions for the reconstruction of destroyed neighborhoods in Homs to stimulate social cohesion. The proposal integrates new with the old in order to connect heritage with a sustainable urban future.

MAGDA MOSTAFA

REGION 5 - AFRICA
CAIRO, EGYPT

Architect, Associate Professor, and Special Needs Designer

Associate Professor of Design
Associate Chair of the Department of Architecture at The American University in Cairo

Co-director of the UNESCO-UIA Architectural Education Commission

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

SDG 10 - REDUCED INEQUALITIES

Sensory Zoning and Circulation Schemes

Awards

UIA International Architecture for All Research Award

ArcVision Women in Architecture Award, Italicementi and the Society of Egyptian Architects

Publications

Learning from Cairo: Global Perspectives and FutureVisions (2014)

"An Architecture for Autism" (2008)

Ted speaker

Project

ASPECTSS Index : Author of the world's first set of evidence-based autism design guidelines. The project is exemplary of changing design standards in order to create architecture that leaves no one behind and is inclusive.

NISHAT AWAN

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
LONDON, UK

Architect and Educator

Senior Lecturer in Visual Cultures at Goldsmiths, University of London
Lecturer in Architecture at the University of Sheffield

Focuses on the reduction of spatial inequalities

**PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE**

Initiatives

Works with OPENkhana, a collaborative that works between architectural, computational and artistic practice

Migrant Narratives of Citizenship exhibition in Yorkshire Sculpture Park using video and digital mapping to explore the paths and spaces transited by refugees

Publications

Diasporic Agencies: Mapping the City Otherwise (2016)

Spatial agency: other ways of doing architecture (2011)

'Digital mapping and agency: The ethics of engaging with places at a distance'

A Topological Atlas of European Belonging

Project

Topological Atlas: A European Research Council funded project working to use spatial architectural tools to investigate the nature of migration and borders in order to reinvent the city. Architectural skill sets are applied to imaginings of the city in map form to reduce inequalities through new conceptions of space.

KIRTEE SHAH

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
AHMEDABAD, INDIA

Architect and NGO Activist

Advisor on 50,000 houses project for the war victims in Sri Lanka.

Focuses on architecture as a means to reduce poverty in India.

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

SDG 1 - NO POVERTY, SDG 10 - REDUCE INEQUALITY

Affiliations

Founder Director of Ahmedabad Study Action Group

Chairman and Chief Architect of Ksa Design Planning Services

Member of the National Task Force on Rural Housing and Habitat

Founder/president of India Habitat Forum (INHAF)

President of Habitat International Coalition

President of Bangalore based Institute for Cultural Research and Action (ICRA)

Founder/chairman of Home Losers' Service Association of Ahmedabad

Consulted with UN agencies, the World Bank, Cities Development Initiatives for Asia

Focus

His architectural career has focused on ways in which architecture in impoverished areas and places hit by natural disasters can be implemented to reduce poverty. His focus in research is on the intersection of rapid urbanization and how it affects poverty and inequality with the intent to minimize both.

EMMA MILOYO

REGION 5 - AFRICA
NAIROBI, KENYA

Architect and President of the Architectural Association of Kenya

Co-Founder of Design Source
Co-founded Women in Real Estate (WIRE)
Director at Kiota School

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY /
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

Top 40
Under 40
Women in
Kenya

Affiliations

First woman to be
President of the
Architectural Association
of Kenya

On the Rio2020
UIA Congress
Scientific Committee

Ted Speaker

Focus

Miloyo's work focuses on affordable housing for all, accessible, safe and clean public spaces, efficient public and non-motorized transport in Kenya. She actively works for gender equality and serves as a role model for women architects in Kenya.

ANNA HERINGER

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
LAUFEN, GERMANY

Architect

Honorary professor of the UNESCO Chair of Earthen Architecture, Building Cultures, and Sustainable Development

Focuses on the use of natural building materials

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

2010 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture
2009 Curry Stone Design Prize
2007 Aga Khan Award
2006, 2008 AR Emerging Architecture Awards
RIBA International Fellowship

Publications

The Future of Architecture (2014)
Authentic Architecture (2013)
Local Solutions for Global Challenges (2010)
Laufenmanifesto
Ted Speaker on building with natural materials

Project

Meti Handmade School:
Project which demonstrates the ability to use innovative design techniques with simple and locally available materials in order to produce meaningful and sustainable architecture that serves socially responsible functions.

MARINA TABASSUM

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
DHAKA, BANGLADESH

Architect and Professor

Practicing Architect and lecturer at international universities

Focusing on inclusive design, encouraging local community support through architecture.

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

2016 Aga Khan Award.
2001 Architect of the Year Award, chosen by the Indian Vice President Bhairon Singh Shekhawat

Affiliations

Director of Academic Program at Bengal Institute for Architecture, Landscapes and Settlements
Principal architect of Marina Tabassum Architects
Visiting professor at the BRAC University and TU Delft

Project

Bait-ur-Rouf Mosque
The design of the mosque emphasized the use of local, natural materials and a small budget. The space itself encourages inclusivity in that it is intended not just for worship, but as a community meeting space for locals.

JYOTI HOSAGRAHAR

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
PARIS, FRANCE

Architect and Heritage Expert

Deputy Director for the World Heritage Centre at UNESCO

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Affiliations

Deputy Director for the World Heritage Centre at UNESCO
Founder of Sustainable Urbanism International, an NGO in Bangalore.
Leads UNESCO Earthen Architecture programme
Was UNESCO Chair in Culture, Habitat, and Sustainable Development in Bangalore

Publications

Indigenous Modernities: Negotiating Architecture and Urbanism

Focus

Expert on heritage, cities, their architecture, history, culture, planning, and sustainable development with a background in setting urban planning policies and working within the UN as well as numerous educational institutions. She also has specialized knowledge of earthen architecture.

TATIANA BILBAO

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
MEXICO CITY, MEXICO

Architect and Educator

Founder of Tatiana Bilbao Estudio

Focuses on design solutions to low cost social housing

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Awards

- 2014 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture Prize
- 2012 Kunstpries Berlin
- 2009 Emerging Voice by the Architecture League of NY

Publications

A House is Not Just a House: Projects on Housing

Exhibition of works at the Louisiana Museum of Art on social housing (2019)

Project

Social Housing Solution: Project demonstrates a low income modular housing solution for Mexico with houses costing \$8,000 and incorporating energy efficient elements. The modular aspect allows buildings to be adaptable to sites and individual needs.

SALMA SAMAR DAMLUJI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
BEIRUT, LEBANON

Architect and Professor

Professor, Binladin Chair for Architecture in the Islamic World at the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture at The American University of Beirut

Co-founder of Daw'an Mud Brick Architecture Foundation in Mukalla, Yemen

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY /
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

- 2015 Académie d'Architecture's Restoration Award
- 2012 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture

Publications

Hassan Fathy Earth & Utopia (2018)

The Architecture of Yemen (2007)

The Architecture of Oman (1998)

The Valley of Mud Brick Architecture (1993)

Project

The Daw'an Mud Brick Architecture Foundation which she founded has undertaken a number of post-war reconstruction projects to restore the cultural heritage of Yemen by rehabilitating mosques using traditional mud brick building techniques such as the Husn Qarn Majid. She is the leading authority on the traditional use of mud brick architecture in Yemen.

SHIGERU BAN

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
TOKYO, JAPAN

Architect

Known for humanitarian efforts in disaster relief using innovations with common materials such as paper for design

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

- 2014 Pritzker Prize
- 2011 Auguste Perret Prize for Technology Applied to Architecture
- 2001 Time magazine Innovator of the Year

Affiliations

Hired by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

Project

Paper Temporary Shelter: Houses were constructed following Typhoon Haiyan using beer crates, sand bags, coconut wood, and plywood combined with a paper tube frame and a thatched palm roof. Design of the temporary shelter uses low cost local materials and an enhanced process to lower construction time.

KATRIN KOOV

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
TALLINN, ESTONIA

Architect and Curator

Chairman of the Estonian Union of Architects

Chair of Landscape Architecture at the Estonian Academy of Arts (EAA)

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY
SDG 1 - NO POVERTY, SDG 10 - REDUCE INEQUALITY

Awards

The government of Estonia presented her with a cultural award for creative achievements

Affiliations

- Editor of Maja, the Estonian Architectural Review
- Co-founder of the architecture firm KAVAKAVA OÜ
- Curator of the Tallinn Architecture Biennial

Focus

Worked on the design of a children's home in Estonia (Kuessaaare lastekodu peremajad) providing services to children with deceased parents.

SUN-YOUNG RIEH

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
SEOUL, KOREA

Architect and Professor

Professor, Department of Architecture at the University of Seoul

Focuses on sustainable architecture and gender conscious environments

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

SDG 5 - ACHIEVE GENDER EQUALITY

Affiliations

Served as a board member for the Architectural Institute of Korea
Board member for the Korean Institute of Architects
Vice president of the Korea Women's Society of Architects & Engineers

Publications

Gender Analysis of the 2030 Seoul Plan" (2013)
"Integration of Sustainability into Architectural Education at Accredited Korean Universities"
"Education for Sustainable Architecture in Asian Countries"
Speaker at the 2015 Gender Summit

Project

Women-Friendly City, Seoul: The project was implemented to make the city safer and accommodating for women through adjustments to urban design. Examples include designating better lit parking spaces with video surveillance. Ensuring the built environment is gender conscious is necessary for future gender equality.

YASAMAN ESMAILI

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
BOSTON, US

Architect and Educator

Founder of Studio Chaha

Focuses on participatory intervention to engage communities and promote equality

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY/ PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

Awards

2018 LafargeHolcim Global Silver Award
2018 AIA National Award of Honor, Goharkhatoon Girlschool in Mazar-I-sharif, Balkh, Afghanistan
2018 Honorable Mention, Zista Competition: Architectural Strategies for Relief after the earthquake in Tehran
2017 LafargeHolcim Regional Gold Award

Project

Color My Home: A project to use architecture and the concept of space to allow community building through the articulation of the concept of 'home' among immigrants. A more inclusive idea of homes and cities is drawn from the participatory nature of the project.

ALEJANDRO ARAVENA

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
CONCEPCIÓN, CHILE

Architect

Architect and Executive Director of the firm Elemental

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

SDG 10 - REDUCED INEQUALITIES

Awards

- 2016 Pritzker Prize
- 2011 Holcim Award Silver
- 2008 Global Award for Sustainable Architecture

Affiliations

- 2009 - 2015 Pritzker Prize Jury Member
- 2016 Director of the Architecture Section of the Venice Biennale
- International Fellow of the Royal Institute of British Architects

Focus

Focuses on social housing solutions and authored *Los Hechos de la Arquitectura* (ARQ, 1999), *El Lugar de la Arquitectura* (ARQ, 2002) and the monograph *Elemental: Incremental Housing and Participatory Design Manual*. His work focuses on innovation in social housing to minimize inequality and poverty.

ABEER SEIKALY

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
AMMAN, JORDAN

Architect, Artist, and Designer

Architect whose research focus is on using material textile technologies to provide housing solutions for refugees and those in need of temporary housing

PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

SDG 10 - REDUCED INEQUALITIES

Awards

- Featured on the UN's Women in Science Podcast
- 2012 Lexus Design Award

Affiliations

- Directed the first contemporary art fair in Jordan in 2010
- Ted speaker about humanitarian relief efforts in relation to architectural research

Project

Weaving a Home: The project implements material technology to solve climactic and mobility problems to design a smarter and more adaptable solution for temporary refugee housing while also affording increased quality of life through good design

**PANEL 6
DESIGN FOR
PARTNERSHIPS OF
CHANGE**

MPHO MATSIPA

REGION 5 - AFRICA
JOHANNESBURG, SOUTH AFRICA

Architect, Curator, and Assistant Professor

Lecturer at University of the Witwatersrand School of Architecture and Planning

Researcher at Wits Institute for Social and Economic Research

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

SDG 17 - PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS

Affiliations

UIA 2014 Durban Conference Speaker

Adjunct Assistant Professor at Columbia GSAPP

Published articles in *Art South Africa*, *The Architectural Review* and *Thesis 11*

Exhibitions

Curator of the 2018 *African Mobilities* Exhibit at the Architekturmuseum, Munich

Curator of Studio X Johannesburg (2016)

Curator of the South Africa Pavilion in the 2008 Venice Biennale

Project

African Mobilities Exhibit (2018): an exhibition investigating the relationship between architecture and mobility/migration issues in Africa and how new architectural typologies emerge from these issues. The exhibition includes collaborative workshops with 14 international cities, encouraging partnerships for change and research.

EYAL WEIZMAN

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
LONDON, UK

Architect, Professor, and Human Rights Activist

Professor of Spatial and Visual Cultures and Founding Director of the Centre for Research Architecture at Goldsmiths

Focuses on using architectural skills to expose human rights violations

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

SDG 16 - PEACE AND JUSTICE, SDG 17 - PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS

Affiliations

Founder of the research agency Forensic Architecture

Co-founder of the research collective DAAR - Decolonizing Art and Architecture

Publications

Forensic Architecture: Violence at the Threshold of Detectability (2017)

The Conflict Shoreline (2015)

The Least of all Possible Evils (2011)

Hollow Land (2007)

A Civilian Occupation (2003)

Project

Forensic Architecture is a research agency at Goldsmith's founded by Eyal Weizman which focuses on using architectural skill sets in spatial investigations to both study and draw attention to human rights violations in countries all over the world. It aims to produce architectural evidence to be used to ensure accountability for unjust action.

LA-MÁS

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
LOS ANGELES, US

Nonprofit Architecture Firm

Focuses on sustainable local community development by partnering with local businesses

Co-executive Directors:
Helen Leung (left) and Elizabeth Timme

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2019 Los Angeles Business Council (LABC), Architectural Design Award
- 2018 Emerging Voices Award
- 2017 American Planning Association (APA) California Chapter, Award of Excellence

Affiliations

- (Helen Leung)
- Serves on the Los Angeles City Planning Commission
- Fellowship at the Office of Sustainable Housing & Communities at the U.S. Department of Housing & Urban Development
- Worked at the Office of Political Affairs at the White House

Project

LA Storefronts Project : LA-Mas offers local businesses free design solutions for storefronts and community areas in order to revitalize local economies and bring vibrancy to neighborhoods. Leung is a frequent speaker on the importance of community engagement and collaboration in architecture to work on a micro scale and be a driver of equitable and inclusive development in areas of low economic status.

TATJANA SCHNEIDER

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
BRAUNSCHWEIG, GERMANY

Architect and Professor

Professor and Head of the Institute for History and Theory of Architecture and the City at the Technical University of Braunschweig

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

SDG 17 - PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS

Affiliations

- Founder of Spatial Agency
- Principal Investigator of the project Urban Education Live (UEL)
- Founder member of the architectural co-operative Glasgow Letters on Architecture and Space and the Radical Architectures Network

Publications

- Spatial agency: Other Ways of Doing Architecture* (2011)
- Flexible Housing* (2007)
- Agency: Working With Uncertain Architectures* (2009)

Project

Urban Education Live (UEL) : An EU funded project which creates a network of partner organizations, including NGOs and civic organizations across Europe to collaborate in strategizing solutions for urban development. It runs a variety of outreach programs, implementing new ideas, and setting up local places to discuss and rethink space.

ERSELA KRIPA

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
TIRANA, ALBANIA

Architect and Assistant Professor

Albanian architect who is co-founder of architecture firm AGENCY in the US, teaches in El Paso, and has worked on several development-related interventions in Albania

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2018 Emerging Voices award from The Architectural League of New York
- 2010 Rome Prize in Architecture
- 2011 Architect Magazine's Emerging Talents
- 2016 DISCREET Fellow in Residence at the Berlin Biennale

Publications

- FRONTS: Security and the Developing World* (2018)
- "How Architecture is Aiding Detention at the U.S.- Mexico Border" (2018)
- Nation Building Aesthetics* (2009)
- TedxElPaso speaker

Project

Architectural interventions have included the temporary installation of a fixture at the US-Mexico borderwall as social commentary on the border (above left) and initiatives to encourage local consideration of recycling in Tirana, a city where it is not prominent, such as with the Remix project (above right).

NABEEL HAMDHI

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
OXFORD, UK

Architect and Professor

Professor emeritus of Housing and Urban Development of the Oxford Brooks University and founder of the program on Development Practice

Prominent figure known for participatory planning initiatives

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

SDG 17 - PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS

Publications

- The Placemaker's Guide to Building Community* (2010)
- Urban Futures: Economic Growth and Poverty Reduction* (2005)
- Small Change: About the Art of Practice and the Limits of Planning in Cities* (2004)
- Action Planning for Cities: A Guide for Community Practice* (1997)
- Housing without Houses: Participation, Flexibility, Enablement* (1995)

Focus

His work focuses on inciting change through grassroots efforts by encouraging participatory methods and small-scale change as an approach to gradually achieving larger scale change. His research on innovative collaborative methods for urban development have led to his consultation for governmental and UN agencies, exemplifying multi-scaled partnerships for change.

SAHAR QAWASMI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
RAMALLAH, PALESTINE

Architect, Artist, and Educator on Cultural Heritage

Architect at Riwaq working on conservation of historic buildings in Palestine

Co-founder of Sakiya, a cultural program to promote knowledge about agriculture and heritage

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

2017 Visible Award Shortlist for Sakiya

2007 American Institute of Architects (AIA) Award

Affiliations

Organized the first Qalandiya International Biennale to promote Palestinian culture and architecture

2012 coordinated the 4th Riwaq Biennale

Project

Sakiya - Art/Science/Agriculture: A residency program which works to preserve local traditions and merge them with ecological practice. It established a "Garden Laboratory", a Compost center and an Open Source Library. The goal is to integrate agriculture and knowledge production into the built environment in Palestine.

PATRICIA ANAHORY

REGION 5 - AFRICA
PRAIA, CAPE VERDE

Architect, Researcher, and Designer

Co-founded Xu:collective and Parenthesis, interdisciplinary art collective focused on art, space, and dialogue

Founding director of the research center CIDLOT at the University of Cape Verde focusing on urban growth and development

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE /
PANEL 3: RESILIENT COMMUNITIES

Affiliations

2017 Juror for the Africa Architecture Awards

Project Manager for the Africa Innovation Summit

Projects

Praia city exchange for the Columbia University's African Mobilities Project: The exchange investigated how narratives shape the identity of Cape Verde and intersect with ideas of identity across space and territory

Focus

Anahory has founded a number of interdisciplinary collectives focusing on the intersection of architecture, environment, art, and space. The collaboratives founded were based on participatory methods to understand spaces and to innovate ways to visually convey this exploration.

SANJEEV SHANKAR

REGION 4 - ASIA AND OCEANIA
BANGALORE, INDIA

Architect, Researcher, and Artist

Founder of a research-based architecture studio in Bangalore, focusing on incorporating participatory methods with sustainable material usage

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
PANEL 2: RETHINKING RESOURCES

Awards

- 2017 National Geographic Society Expedition Council grant
- 2010 10 Great Ideas to change the world' Award at Indian Institute of Technology
- 2009 shortlisted for Emerging Architecture award at RIBA

Exhibitions

- 2016 *Enabling Economic Growth*, India
- 2011 *Jugaad Urbanis: Resourceful Strategies for Indian Cities*, New York
- 2008 *48 Degrees*, Public Eco Art Festival, India

Project

Jugaad:
In collaboration with 90 residents of New Delhi Shankar created a public art installation made completely from recycled oil cans used by local residents. The project demonstrates how participatory construction can encourage new perspectives on recycling of materials and sustainability through architectural methods.

NOOR MARJI

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
AMMAN, JORDAN

Architect and Designer

Award winning architect and student of urban planning focusing on projects to challenge the civic role of architecture

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE /
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- LafargeHolcim Awards 2017 Middle East Africa - Next Generation Prize
- Tamayouz International 2016 Award
- Jordanian Engineers Association Award

Initiatives

Won several awards for the project design of Square One, an urban library and learning center, which encourages a rethinking of the education system in Jordan in order to be more oriented to the social

Project design to rethink waste management networks in Amman

Project

Designed a pop-up library project, with libraries intended for us by Syrian and Iraqi refugees. The libraries were constructed entirely out of everyday waste materials such as bottles and newspapers. The intent was both to bring a library to refugees as well as show children the potential to build and shape their environments with common materials.

MARIANA PESTANA

REGION 1 - WESTERN EUROPE
PORTO, PORTUGAL

Architect and Curator

Lecturer in Spatial Design at Central Saint Martins/ Chelsea College of Arts and in Design Interactions at the Royal College of Arts

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
PANEL 1: CLIMATE ADAPTATION

Affiliations

Curator Istanbul Design Biennale 2020

Co-founded a collective called The Decorators, developing curatorial/research projects through interventions

Exhibitions

Eco-Visionaries

The Future Starts Here exhibition at V&A Museum, London

The Public Age Meeting House - mobile meeting space to foster wellbeing among the elderly

Project

Eco-Visionaries: Art and Architecture After the Anthropocene:

An exhibition at MAAT, Lisbon. Mariana Pestana regularly curates prominent exhibitions related to the role of architecture in the future of climate change. The exhibitions serve as inspiration to take climate action.

MARJETICA POTRČ

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
LJUBLJANA, SLOVENIA

Architect, Artist and Professor

Incorporates participatory process with innovative design solutions in informal communities

Former Professor of social practice at the University of Fine Arts/HFBK in Hamburg

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE /
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

2007 Vera List Center for Arts and Politics Fellowship at The New School in New York

2004 AICA-USA Second-Place Award for Best Architecture or Design Show

2000 Hugo Boss Prize, administered by the Guggenheim Museum

Exhibitions

Venice Biennale (2003 and 2009)

Barbican Art Galleries in London (2007)

Sao Paulo Biennial (1996 and 2006)

Guggenheim Museum in New York (2001)

Project

Hybrid House: Caracas, West Bank, West Palm Beach Exhibition demonstrates architectural potential for cultural critique through calling attention to areas in conflict.

She also has collaborated to create Dry Toilet in Caracas: an ecological, waterless toilet installed in an area of the city with no access to sewage.

STUDIO BASAR

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
BUCHAREST, ROMANIA

Architecture Firm

Architectural firm focusing on public actions, community projects and educational programmes

Founded by **Alex Axinte** (left) and Cristi Borcan

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE

SDG 17 - PARTNERSHIP FOR THE GOALS

Awards

2017 National Cultural Fund - "Cultural activation in public space" category - Prize

2017 Curry Stone Design Prize - Social Design Circle Honoree

Publications

Searching for the In Between City

Public works - the reconnections of communities in the dormitory neighborhoods

Project

City School : The Library from Militari:

Workshops were initiated to encourage discussion around the concept of public space in an attempt to help shape needs of communities in Romania. A reorganization of a library was done to allow new knowledge and participatory urban planning education to be shared.

CLUSTER CAIRO

REGION 5 - AFRICA
CAIRO, EGYPT

Architect, Curator, and Researcher

Beth Stryker (left), Co-founder of Cairo Lab for Urban Studies, Training, and Environmental Research (CLUSTER)

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/ PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards and Exhibitions

2017 Curry Stone Design Prize

Curator Downtown Contemporary Arts Festival in Cairo

Curator for Beirut Art Center

Curator for the AIA/Center for Architecture in New York

Publications

"Street Vendors and the Contestation of Public Space" (2017)

"Archiving the City in Flux" (2013)

co-editor of *Learning from Cairo* (2013)

Creative Initiatives: Economic Impact on Downtown Cairo

Project

Cluster focuses on urban research emphasizing collaborative efforts for transformation. Examples include an initiative to explore the relationship of street vendors to the city, workshops helping young designers become in contact with local makers, and workshops focusing on the ability of architecture to be a catalyst for change and resistance, creating more inclusive environments.

JEAN-CHARLES TALL

REGION 5 - AFRICA
DAKAR, SENEGAL

Architect and Educator

Founder and President of the Board of the Collège Universitaire d'Architecture de Dakar

Co-director of J&T Architectes et Associés

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
 PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Affiliations

President of the Ordre des Architectes du Sénégal
 Member of the scientific committee of the Dakar International Art Biennale
 Involved with the Doual'Art Triennale in Cameroon

Member of the Comité Supérieur des Monuments Historiques du Sénégal
 Collaborated with MASS Design group on an Aga Khan award winning school in Rwanda (above)

Focus

He focuses on educative workshops, encouraging students to visit and consider informal settlements in Dakar. As founder of the first architecture school in Senegal he has been actively involved in encouraging education, collaboration, and architectural approaches working against developmental inequalities.

LINDSAY BREMNER

REGION 5 - AFRICA
JOHANNESBURG, SOUTH AFRICA

Architect and Professor

Zambian born architect, researching the intersections of architecture, geology, and politics specifically focused on Africa and Asia

Professor and former Director of Architectural Research in the School of Architecture and the Built Environment at the University of Westminster

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE/
 PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Affiliations

Worked for the executive Committee of the Johannesburg City Council, in the departments of urban planning, housing, urbanism and environment
 Formerly on the Board of Advisors of the International Archive of Women in Architecture (IAWA)

Publications

Monsoon [+ other] waters (2019)
Geological Health 2015)
Writing the City into Being: Essays on Johannesburg 1998 – 2008 (2010)
Recovering from Apartheid (2008)

Project

Sans Souci Community Cinema Project: Project in Sewoto South Africa to transform a ruined historic cinema into a community meeting place with no funding, enacted through participatory planning and community activation of the space. Collaborative efforts worked to restore the space as one for workshops and events while revitalizing a historical landmark.

MABEL O. WILSON

REGION 3 - THE AMERICAS
NEW YORK, US

Architect, Professor, and Curator

Professor of Architecture, Planning and Preservation
Co-director of Global Africa Lab
Associate Director at the Institute for Research in African American Studies at Columbia University

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE /
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Awards

- 2019 Educator/Mentor honor from Architectural Record's Women in Architecture Design Leadership Program.
- 2019 Arts and Letters Award from the American Academy of Arts and Letters
- 2011 United States Artists Ford Fellow in Architecture and Design

Publications

- Begin with the Past: Building the National Museum of African American History and Culture* (2016)
- Negro Building: Black Americans in the World of Fairs and Museums* (2012)
- Building Race and Nation: Slavery and Dispossessions Influence on American Civic Architecture* (2020)

Project

Founder of [Who Builds Your Architecture](#) - a collective working towards research to make connections between construction and architects to ensure equality and fair practice. The project intends to educate the architectural profession about fair labor, globalization, and the relation of architecture to social inequalities.

SANDI HILAL

REGION 2 - EASTERN EUROPE/MIDDLE EAST
BETHLEHEM, PALESTINE

Architect, Artist, and Peace Activist

Active player in refugee camp relief, reform, and education programs in Palestine

Uses architectural design interventions as mechanisms for social change

PANEL 6: PARTNERSHIPS OF CHANGE /
PANEL 5: INCLUSIVITY

Affiliations

- Headed the infrastructure and Camp Improvement Program in the West Bank at United Nations Relief and Works Agency
- Co-founder of Campus in Camps, an experimental educational program established in a Bethlehem refugee camp
- Co Founder of DAAR - Decolonizing Art, Architecture Residency

Publications

- Permanent Temporariness* (2018)
- Architecture after Revolution* (2014)
- Senza Stato una Nazione* (2003)

Project

DAAR - Decolonizing Architecture Art and residency project - [The Concrete Tent](#): One of many spatial interventions by DAAR, the Concrete Tent corresponds to the book *Permanent Temporariness*. The structure serves as a communal meeting place for ideas as well as a commentary on injustice, and functions to reduce inequality as well as encourage peace.

Index

Design for Climate Adaptation	23
Katherine Richardson	24
Turenscape	25
Raumlabor Berlin	26
Al Borde	27
Hoang Thuc Hao	28
Carola Hein	29
Kunlé Adeyemi	30
Kotchakorn Voraakhom	31
Cooking Sections	32
Maibritt Pedersen Zari	33
Gita Goven	34
Mikkel K. Kragh	35
Chris Luebke	36
Danna Masad	37
Edward Ng	38
East Coast Architects	39
Design For Rethinking Resources	41
Ronald Rael	42
Paolo Cascone	43
Majd Mashharawi	44
Superuse Studios	45
Thomas Lommée	46
Anupama Kundoo	47
Carlo Ratti	48
Stéphanie Chaltiel	49
Anne Lacaton	50
Martin Rajnis	51
Diébédo Francis Kéré	52
Alexander Brodsky	53
Salto Architects	54
David Benjamin	55
Eko Prawoto	56
Comunal Taller	57
Billie Faircloth	58
Boonserm Premthada	59
Design for Resilient Communities	61
Natalia Fishman-Bekmambetova	62
Alejandro Echeverri	63
Jana Revedin	64
Emanuel Admassu	65
Anna Rubbo	66
Young Joon Kim	67
Ruta Leitanaite	68
Juan Du	69
Alfred Omenya	70
Gerhard Schmitt	71
Olga Aleksakova	72
Martha Thorne	73
Yaşar Adnan Adanali	74
Hsieh Ying-Chun	75
Elisabete França	76
Peter Mould	77
Bige Tunçer	78
Zegeye Cherenet Mamo	79

Design for Health	81
Christian Benimana	82
Riccardo Vannucci	83
Doreen Adengo	84
Line Ramstad	85
Peter Williams	86
Orkid Studio	87
Arif Hasan	88
Rozana Montiel	89
Sierra Bainbridge	90
Christopher Webster	91
Dk Osseo-Asare	92
Amale Andraos	93
Design for Inclusivity	95
Mariam Kamara	96
Suad Amiry	97
Alfredo Brillembourg	98
Yasmeen Lari	99
Asiye Etafuleni	100
Flora Samuel	101
Marwa Al-Sabouni	102
Magda Mostafa	103
Nishat Awan	104
Kirtee Shah	105
Emma Miloyo	106
Anna Heringer	107
Marina Tabassum	108
Jyoti Hosagrahar	109
Tatiana Bilbao	110
Salma Samar Damluji	111
Shigeru Ban	112
Katrin Koov	113
Sun-Young Rieh	114
Yasaman Esmaili	115
Alejandro Aravena	116
Abeer Seikaly	117
Design for Partnerships of Change	119
Mpho Matsipa	120
Eyal Weizman	121
La-Más	122
Tatjana Schneider	123
Ersela Kripa	124
Nabeel Hamdi	125
Sahar Qawasmi	126
Patricia Anahory	127
Sanjeev Shankar	128
Noor Marji	129
Mariana Pestana	130
Marjetica Potrč	131
Studio Basar	132
Cluster Cairo	133
Jean-Charles Tall	134
Lindsay Bremner	135
Mabel O. Wilson	136
Sandi Hilal	137

